

What is Artificial Intelligence?

Imagine your very smart friend who thinks, learns, and can solve problems. Now imagine if we could make a computer that could do the same things. It's all about Artificial Intelligence, or, as it's commonly referred to, AI.

That is to say, giving a computer brain is like AI. What I mean is, they're making those machines powerful enough to do something that you'd expect to have to be done by a human. These smart machines can build things, map data, learn, make decisions and really get smarter over time.

So imagine AI as the computer being taught to behave more like a human. AI systems learn surprisingly well from the data that we provide to them, just as we do. They can then do tasks or solve problems using what they've learned.

Here are some everyday examples of AI:

1. Siri or Alexa, for instance, who can understand your voice and give you an answer to a question
2. Some video recommendations on Netflix or YouTube that tell you videos that you might like.
3. The self driving cars that can drive on roads and avoid obstacles
4. Capabilities to identify people in photos with facial recognition systems

In the meantime, we'll hear people refer to "machine learning" when discussing AI. Actually, machine learning is a part of AI. It's like a special tool in the AI toolbox. If AI is making a computer learn to be smart, machine learning is making it learn to learn on its own.

We feed the computer lots of examples and teach it patterns. It is a bit like teaching a child to distinguish animals. We don't say the exact thing that tells the child it is a cat, and just how does a cat make it a cat? Instead, they are shown lots of pictures of cats and dogs, and they learn to tell them apart.

In machine learning, for example, we might even configure a computer to show it thousands of pictures of cats and dogs. It learns to tell the differences and can then find cats and dogs in new pictures it hasn't seen before.

The reason AI and machine learning are so cool is because they can solve problems we couldn't solve, they can make things easier in many ways. For doctors to diagnose diseases, for scientists to predict weather patterns, or even for us to explore space ... they can help!

Yet it's essential to keep in mind that although AI can perform some unbelievable things, it remains manmade and at the time of when it does. AI is something that doesn't have feelings or consciousness, like we do. But it's not a replacement for human intelligence and creativity.

With additional development of AI, we are all continually opening new doors of what technology can do for us. Who knows? Maybe the future AI can help us solve some of our world's biggest problems.

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!

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